

THE GRADES OF REALITY IN THE LIGHT OF GAUḌAPĀDA AND ŚAṄKARA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The article attempts to explore the concept of the grades of reality in the philosophical framework of Gauḍapāda. The monistic philosophical systems cannot ignore their philosophical responsibility to explain the fact of multiplicity of this empirical world. This is also applicable for the philosophy of Gauḍapāda. Reality, for Gauḍapāda, is one and non-dual (*ekamevādvitīyam*). In the philosophical tradition of India both Gauḍapāda and Śaṅkara are considered as the celebrated masters of Advaita tradition. Gauḍapāda is considered as the grand preceptor of Śaṅkara. Gauḍapāda has argued that the notion of non-duality, in his philosophy, is consistent with the multiplicity of the world of experience. Unlike Gauḍapāda, Śaṅkara has directly distinguished three levels of reality, viz., *prātibhāsika*, *vyāvahārika* and *pāramārthika*. Gauḍapāda does not make any such clear-cut distinction of the grades of reality (*prātibhāsika*, *vyāvahārika* and *pāramārthika*); rather he has established the identity between the object of experience and the content of dream to establish unreality of the world of experience. In this article a close reading of Gauḍapāda's *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* in the light of its commentary by Śaṅkara may throw some light on this issue. The philosophical system of Gauḍapāda has its commitment and philosophical justification to the degrees of reality. Though there is a substantial amount of text-based research on the philosophy of Gauḍapāda, yet an extensive and critical study on this issue is a long-felt desideratum.

Key words: Grades of Reality, Multiplicity, Illusoriness, Waking state, State of dream, Unreality

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This article intends to explore the importance of grades of reality in the philosophy of Gauḍapāda. Reality, for Gauḍapāda, is one and non-dual (*ekamevādviṭīyam*). The historians of Indian Philosophy are not unanimous about the time of him. But here a question arises: How then the fact of multiplicity of the world be explained? Is the status of the world fictitious? How can the object of our experience be fictitious like sky-lotus? Does he deny the reality of this empirical world altogether? To speak philosophically, Gauḍapāda had to give notion of the status of the empirical world endowed with plurality. A close reading of Gauḍapāda's *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* with its commentary by Śāṅkara on it, may throw some light on this issue. The philosophical system of Gauḍapāda has its commitment and philosophical justification to the degrees of reality. Though there is a substantial amount of text-based research on the philosophy of Gauḍapāda, yet an extensive and critical study on this issue is a long-felt desideratum. The main concern of this paper is to fulfil this lacuna.

It is indeed true that in order to prove the illusoriness of this empirical world from ultimate standpoint, Gauḍapāda establishes an identity between the object of experience and the content of dream. In Śāṅkara's philosophy, there is clear admission of different level of reality based on *prātibhāsika*, *vyāvahārika* and *pāramārthika* standpoint. But, in Gauḍapāda's *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* we do not see any direct explicit admission of gradation of reality. To put it differently, if we closely analyse arguments from dream analogy in order to explain the status of the world of multiplicity, there is an indirect admission of the grades of reality.

I

In the philosophical tradition of India both Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara are considered as the celebrated masters of Advaita tradition.ⁱ Gauḍapāda has argued that his non-dualism is consistent with the multiplicity of the world of experience. Unlike Gauḍapāda, Śāṅkara has directly distinguished three levels of reality, viz., *prātibhāsika*, *vyāvahārika* and *pāramārthika*. But, Gauḍapāda does not make any such clear-cut distinction of the grades of reality (*prātibhāsika*, *vyāvahārika* and *pāramārthika*); rather he has established the identity between the object of experience and the content of dream to establish unreality of the world of experience.ⁱⁱ The objects of experience are only mental creations, according to Gauḍapāda. He has argued in favour of the view that the objects of experience are only mental creationsⁱⁱⁱ The world of experience exists only in the vibrations of mind (*cittaspanḍita*).^{iv} In order to prove identity between awaking state and that of dream Gauḍapāda maintains that the objects of dream exist so far as they are perceived in the state of dream (*cittakāla*). But on the other hand, the objects experienced in the waking state are *dvyayakāla* (the object exists as long as the notion of *grāhya-grāhaka bhāva* remains).^v Both the objects of dream and waking state are the products of imagination (*kalpita eva sarve*), according to Gauḍapāda.^{vi}

Gauḍapāda has tried to establish the illusoriness of the world on the basis of the analogy of dream. In the *Vaitathya prakaraṇa* and *Alātaśānti prakaraṇa*, he has established the non-dual nature of the world of plurality on the basis of the analogy of the dream states and waking states. It is observed that he begins his philosophical endeavour with the hypothesis that all the dream objects are illusory. Gauḍapāda argues that the

objects perceived in the state of dream are considered to be false, because being confined within a body they become subject of perception. The dream objects like chariot, mountains etc. can never be accommodated in the body of a person who is dreaming. So, their existence is false. In this connection, it may be pointed out that *samvṛtatva* (being enclosed) is not with reference to *bhūtas* but with reference to the place (*pradeśa*).^{vii} It may be argued against Gauḍapāda that the objects like mountain or chariot are not situated within a body. The person who is dreaming may travel to mountains, which is manifested in a dream, may be regarded as real. Gauḍapāda's reply to this argument is that it is impossible for a person to move actually to the places manifested in a dream within a short span of dreaming. How is it actually possible for a person to travel thousands of miles during a short period dream? The state of dream hardly stays one hour. Moreover, in several cases it is observed that the person suddenly awakes from the state of dream. He, then, does not find himself in the situation or place where he was actually in the state of dream/ during the period of dream. So, the objects manifested in a dream are not factually within the body itself.^{viii} The dream experiences are unreal due to the absence of the actual place and time associated with the state of dream. This unreality can be judged from the point of view of waking state. The unreality of the manifest content of the dream is proved with respect to the spatio-temporal consideration. Gauḍapāda here offers several similar arguments to prove unreality of the objects of external world.^{ix}

What has been seen is that the state of waking is on par with that of dream. The objects experienced in waking state are, as if, perceived as the content of dream. That is why, whatever is seen in the waking state and in dream, is illusory. Moreover, it is argued that both the contents of

dream and waking states are unreal upon the general principle that whatever is absent from the very beginning and going to have an end, is *vitatha* in the present also.^x

Again, a question may arise: Why do we consider the objects manifested in dream as *vitatha*? The answer to this question may be given from the *saprayojanatā* point of view ('having some purpose'). The concept of *saprayojanatā* gets contradicted in the state of waking. Suppose, a person is dreaming that some sumptuous foods have been served to him but, in the waking-state he is not being able to gratify his hunger with those foods. The *saprayojanatā* ('having some purpose'^{xi}) of a food in the waking-state is contradicted by the dream state. So, the objects of the waking state are at the same level with that of dream because each is contradicted by other. The objects of waking state, as securing the nature of *anyathābhāva* (different state) and being changeful in nature, gets contradicted in a different state must be considered as *mithyā* (false)^{xii}

It may further be argued that both the dream contents and the objects of waking state fail to give an account for proving the illusoriness of the empirical world since they are different from each other. The objects of dream are sometimes abnormal and strange, unprecedented and fantastic. Even, the contents of dream are not exactly what we experience in the waking state. And here there is no room for *saprayojanatā* argument as stated earlier. Is it, therefore, justified to consider the dream as a unique state having no juxtaposition to the waking state? Is the dreamer also a different being to create such a fantastic, strange and unprecedented objects in the dream? So, it becomes impossible to draw a conclusion about the *vaitathya* (unreality) of objects in *jāgrat* (awaking state) from what we

experience in the *svapna*. The answer to this argument is that what is experienced in dream (*svapnadṛśya*) is a wonderful (*apūrva*). But it does not imply that the dreamer is a different being. It is a matter of *sthānamāhātmya*. Similarly, *apūrvatva* is nothing but a feature of the dream-state. The things experienced or done in the dream state may appear as unreal in the waking-state. But these things are considered to be real by the dreamer for a time being. So, the *vaitathya*(unreality) of objects depends upon no matter they are normal or abnormal. But it solely rests upon the fact whether they are capable of being contradicted in other state or not.^{xiii}

It is important to point out that both in the state of dream and waking state, our mind plays a crucial role. Being impelled by *māyā* mind moves and creates the appearance of the plural world. The mind, according to Gauḍapāda, is non-dual as it is identical with the self. But it owes to false duality and the consequence of which is *samsāra*.^{xiv} The objects of waking state and the dream contents are exhibited through *māyā*. The objects of waking state and that of dream are similar in the sense that both of them become subject of experience and unreal. Gauḍapāda here seems to offer some reasons in favor of his Vijnānavādins' point of view regarding unreality of the external things. According to him, external objects are unreal but they appear to be real. They are as false as the dream experiences. But they become subject of cognition only by our mind (*cittadṛśya*). In order to draw a similarity between the state of dream and that of waking state, Gauḍapāda has brought them under a causal nexus. Dream and wakefulness are identical on the ground that the cause and its effect are always of the same nature. There is no difference between the experience of dream and that of waking state. The waking state is considered as

the cause of dream state. If a state of dream is false waking state also becomes falsified. Here a pertinent remark has been made by Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya. According to him, dream is real only to the dreamer. Similarly, wakefulness is too real only to the unenlightened people.^{xv} It is interesting to pass a note here that wakefulness or *jāgarita* is the cause of dream from the *vyāvahārika* point of view.^{xvi}

From the above discussion, a question becomes inevitable that if the entities of the state of dream and that of wakefulness are unreal, what else is real to cognize them? Is there anything real at all? In reply to this question, he may have introduced the notion of the self in his *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā*. The concept of self is accepted in his philosophical framework to give a logical explanation to the question raised above because the self is one and only to cognize the entities of both the state of dream and that of wakefulness. Through *māyā* the self creates the contents of dream and external world. The contents created in the mind and the things exhibited in the world of experience are nothing but an imagination of the self. The variety and multiplicity we experience in both the states are illusory. It is always conditioned by *māyā*. According to Gauḍapāda, the *advaita*(non-dual) self is only real.^{xvii}

So far, we have given the philosophical explanation of the illusoriness of this world of experience from the point of view of dream analogy. But now let us give some illustrations of illusoriness of this empirical world from the examples in the waking state. In the darkness, a piece of rope is mistakenly cognised to be a snake for a 'stream of water' (*udakadhārā*). Similarly, due to ignorance, the self is appeared to us as many. After the correction of error, the rope is manifested to us as rope and likewise, after realisation of the self as the non-dual reality, the manifold appearance of the world disappears.^{xviii} The objects of this empirical world are appeared to be real since they become the subject of experience (*upalambhāt*) and also

become subject to practical purposes (*samācārāt*). But these two reasons are not sufficient to prove them as real. Gauḍapāda's view of illusoriness of this empirical world has been depicted in the *Alātaśānti prakaraṇa* of *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā*. In this *prakaraṇa* work he has offered some arguments from the analogy of *alāta* (fire-brands) in order to show that the appearance of consciousness in manifold forms is due to *māyā*. The only reality, for Gauḍapāda, is unmoving, nonchanging pure consciousness (*acala vijñaptimātra*).^{xix}

In a contrast to the above view, Ācārya Śaṅkara refutes the contention of Gauḍapāda that the experiences in the waking state is identical with that of dream. In the Śaṅkara's *Brahmasūtrabhāṣya*, he has clearly presented his philosophical position regarding this issue. He maintains that the external objects can exist independent of their ideas in the mind. Here, Ācārya Śaṅkara has vehemently criticized the Buddhist Idealist doctrine. The Buddhist philosophers subscribe to the view that the only ideas can exist. The external world, for them, is non-existent. A philosophical question may arise at this point: Is the objective world absolutely non-existent like any fictitious entity (hare's horn)? Or is it unreal even as the objects perceived in a dream is unreal? Śaṅkara has repudiated the above explained Buddhist Idealist view. According to him, the empirical world is, after all, the object of experience through our senses. So, the existence of it cannot be denied, nor can it be fictitious like hare's horn. The Buddhist philosophers may argue that they do not render that they are conscious about no object, but only that what is perceived in their consciousness merely manifests as something external. But in that case, the very existence of consciousness itself justifies the existence of external entities apart from consciousness, since man is conscious of the object of perception and not merely of perception. Śaṅkara argues that to explain any internal cognition 'as something external' is to mean that the external world is real. If it is not real, the expression like 'as something external' would have no meaning.^{xx}

Śaṅkara has, thus, established the fact of the existence of external objects.

Śaṅkara has not admitted the empirical reality of the entities of the waking state in an impulsive fashion; even nor has it been articulated by the necessity of dialectical confrontation with the Buddhists. This is the logical outcome of his philosophical articulation of the theory of superimposition (*adhyāsa*)^{xxi}. Śaṅkara's main point of divergence with Gauḍapāda is that Śaṅkara's philosophy has recognised the status of this empirical world. He does not defy this world endowed with plurality as a mere dream stuff. The philosophy of Śaṅkara is, epistemologically, a realist philosophy. Then snake-rope, for Śaṅkara's formulation, is not merely an idea. The snake is presented to a percipient as *anirvacanīya* entity and it can be sublated by the cognition of its empirically valid substratum, rope. The world of experience possesses a greater reality than the entities of the illusory level (*prātibhāsika*). The percipient belongs to this world of multiplicity and the abode of which is *advaita Brahman*. Thus, Śaṅkara has formulated the theory of *adhyāsa* to account for the doctrine of three-fold reality in his philosophical framework. Our religious and ethical life is necessary to understand this world as actually non-dual and only the cancellation of this empirical manifold is possible. The 'unsublatability' or *avādhyatva* is the criterion of absolute reality for the Advaitins. We arrive at the philosophical insight that the functional reality of this empirical world acts as a mean between illusory reality and absolute reality since, the illusory reality of the snake-rope is to the functional reality of the rope and so is the functional reality of this empirical world to the trans phenomenal reality of *advaita Brahman*.^{xxii} This philosophical realization unfolds the panorama of our purposeful life endowed with manifold of activities and rich in its content. Śaṅkara has probably articulated the theory of *adhyāsa* in his metaphysics to offer a key to explore the unending mystery of life.^{xxiii} In a critical observation on the philosophy of Gauḍapāda it can be pointed out that the

possibility of this empirical plural world is excluded in his philosophical framework by its dogmatic identification of the state of dream and that of waking.

So far, we have observed the philosophy of Gauḍapādaas presented in his *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* that he has declared *ajātivāda* as the supreme view of reality. In the *Advaita prakaraṇa* of *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā*, it is maintained that non-duality is the ultimate reality.^{xxiv} His view point to the fact that *dvayasatya* is accepted in his philosophical framework to account for the conventional truth of duality, but the ultimate reality is non-dual. *Ajātivāda*, for Gauḍapāda, is the supreme view of reality since, it is not in conflict with any other dualistic views.^{xxv} The main theme of this *Āgamaśāstra* is *ajātivāda* 'absence of birth or production'.^{xxvi} According to Bādarāyaṇa's *Brahmasūtra*,^{xxvii} everything is originated from *advaita Brahman*. Different schools of Indian philosophy maintain that the things are born or produced have their own cause.^{xxviii} The meaning of the term *utpāda* requires to be clarified in order to understand Gauḍapāda's philosophical position regarding *ajātivāda*. According to the opponents, the *utpāda* of a thing may be looked upon from a causal point of view which may be either itself (*sva*), or something other than itself (*para*) or both of them (*ubhaya*) or it may be *ahetu* (not at all a cause). Gauḍapāda here philosophically proclaims that a thing that originates has the state of its becoming or being produced. But, in reality, we find nothing of this kind. The main objective of this discussion about *ajātivāda* is to prove both the views of *satkāryavāda* and *asatkāryavāda* as untenable. Gauḍapāda intends to establish that both the philosophical standpoints of *vastu svataḥ jāyate* and *vastu parataḥ jāyate* are equally untenable. An object can be produced neither *svataḥ* nor *parataḥ*.^{xxix} It may be argued that a pot is produced out of clay and a child is born of a father. But it may be replied that here the word 'birth' has a deluded use and a concept corresponding to the word. Both the word and its corresponding concept are subject to examination. After examination by the

men of discrimination it comes to conclude that the objects, such as a pot or a child, denoted by the terms and conceptualised by the concepts are mere verbal expressions. Furthermore, they argue that the material cause (clay or father) is merely an illustration to support the contention. Whatever is ever-existent cannot be born again. Similarly, the non-existent object cannot be subject to genesis. The hare's horn is an example of non-existent object. Again, objects be simultaneously existent and non-existent, cannot be born because it results in a contradiction. No such contradictory concepts can be associated with an object. So, Gauḍapāda firmly establishes that nothing is subject to born. Gauḍapāda finally denies the theory of causation on the ground that the tenability of the very fact of birth is born again and the fact of causation is far from reason. In order to establish the doctrine of *ajāti* Gauḍapāda has offered several arguments to repudiate *satkāryavāda* (the doctrine of real existence of an effect in its cause prior to its manifestation) and *asatkāryavāda* (the doctrine of real non-existence of an effect in its cause prior to its manifestation). In the *kārikā*, Gauḍapāda has himself referred to both *satkāryavādīns* and *asatkāryavādīns* as his opponents. Gauḍapāda proves that both *satkāryavāda* and *asatkāryavāda* cannot be tenable. His philosophical contention is that to believe in real origination is to believe in the relationship between cause and effect. The Scriptural texts (*Śruti*) admit both the views regarding origination from the existent and from the non-existent. Ācārya Śaṅkara in his commentary on the *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* 3.23 has raised an objection: those who do not accept the phenomenon of actual creation, cannot ratify the authority of the Scriptural texts.^{xxx} In reply to this objection, it may be asserted that in the Scriptural texts the act of creation as actual is accepted, but these texts may have other purposes to cater. But here the philosophical contention is to alleviate or mitigate all the doubts related to the applicability of the subject matter of the Scriptural texts (*Śruti*). The actual purpose of the *Śruti* is not to prove the

phenomenon of creation, but to establish whether the creation of things is considered in the real sense or as a mere illusion.

Again, it is argued that it is logical to understand the empirical world in terms of its direct meaning, if the metaphorical and direct meanings of the word are admitted. It may be replied that the act of creation is unknown to us. There is no other purpose of admitting creation. All the creation, metaphorical or real, is, after all, an apparent creation due to *avidyā*. But it has no real existence from the standpoint of absolute reality. The *Śruti* proclaims that ‘the *ātman* is really changeless’^{xxxix}. The ultimate aim of the *Śruti-vākya* is to establish the eternal changelessness of the *advaita Brahman*. So, the actual import of the Scriptural texts is to prove that “He is one and without a second and is free from birth and death”^{xxxii}.

Ācārya Śāṅkara, on the contrary, upholds an apparent contradictory theory of creation. The classical doctrine of creation in the philosophy of Śāṅkara is defined by Dharmarājadhvarindra in his *Vedāntaparibhāṣā*. This theory is technically known as *asvivartavāda*. *Vivartavāda* is the transformation of the cause into its effect. In this transformation the cause does not lose its real character. Hence, it is characterised as an apparent transformation. Advaita Vedāntins maintain that the empirical world is, after all, an apparent transformation of *advaita Brahman*. This perceptible cosmos, for them, is a mere illusion. So, the world of experience is an illusory appearance. *Brahman* is the only real entity. A more radical Vedāntic view of creation is, on the other hand, Gauḍapāda’s *ajātivāda*. Gauḍapāda subscribes to the view that everything is subject to origination on account of the illusion of experience. It is, therefore, indeed not eternal (*śāśvata*). From the standpoint of absolute reality, everything is unoriginated (*ajam*). Therefore, there is no annihilation (*uchhedah*).^{xxxiii}

A pertinent philosophical problem may arise that these two complementary but apparently antagonistic doctrines emphasise upon different philosophical point of views. All the

soteriological systems of thought have ultimately a pragmatic outlook: the soteriological aim is to eradicate suffering from the individual’s life. Consequently, Vedāntic discourse aims to be pragmatic. Their metaphysical presuppositions may be different but, their ultimate metaphysical goal is the same. It is important to note that the subject-matter of different philosophical systems is less important than their philosophical aims. So, we can find apparently contradictory different philosophical formulations for one doctrine.^{xxxiv} A comparative analysis between *vivartavāda* and *ajātivāda* shows that *vivartavāda* is, after all, an apparent origination of the world and *ajātivāda* is the non-origination of the world in reality. In case of *vivartavāda* the emphasis is laid upon the world of experience to give importance to the minds of ordinary people. Here the non-real transformation of the Absolute in this empirical world takes place. The main focal point of the *ajātivāda* is the absolute and not the world. A close reading of these two doctrines shows that the fundamental concepts of both doctrines is the same. The philosophical discourse of both Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkaracan be juxtaposed in the sense that the empirical world has no ultimate reality. The apparent divergence between their philosophical approaches is entirely a matter of point of view. When an aspirant prospers in transcending the relative attitude, the doctrinal edifice he clings to gets meaningless.

II

But a critical study at once shows that the world is the erroneous creation of the ultimate real *ātman* through his *māyā*. This may refer to a *drṣṭi-srṣṭi-vāda* point of view towards the problem of reality. This concept of Gauḍapāda is replaced by the doctrine of *drṣṭi-srṣṭi* in the philosophy of Śāṅkara. For Śāṅkara, *Īśvara* is the *nimitta kāraṇa* (efficient cause) and *upādāna kāraṇa* (material cause) of this world. According to Śāṅkara, the world where a person lives in must be considered seriously and objectively. The reality of this empirical world, according to

Śāṅkara, is not to be treated as an illusory entity superimposed on *advaita Brahman*. The objective status of this empirical world makes it capable of leading one to the supreme goal of life.^{xxxv} Without the objective status of this world the life in it becomes meaningless and futile. In a comparative study between the philosophy of Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara, let us proceed to observe that the most important philosophical disagreement between them is that Gauḍapāda admits only the immutable Absolute Reality and thereby discarding the possibility of all else as illusory whereas, Śāṅkara, with a more comprehensive and penetrating vision towards varied aspects of life, maintains three grades of reality. Gauḍapāda's philosophical concern is to delineate the nature of the absolute reality. Consistently with his philosophical point of view, Gauḍapāda expresses his little concern for the life of ordinary people of this mundane world. Śāṅkara, on the contrary, articulates his own philosophy with a flexible structure with a view to enlightening the people of this world of experience.

In the light of a critical approach, it is very difficult to agree always with the remark that "...doctrinally, there is no difference whatsoever between what is taught by Gauḍapāda in the *kārikā* and what is expounded by Śāṅkara in his extensive works"^{xxxvi} It is undeniable that both Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara have accepted the immutable *ātman* as the supreme reality. But, the remarkable difference between their philosophies lies in the fact that the doctrine of three-fold reality (*sattātraividhyavāda*) is not the philosophical foundation of Gauḍapāda's philosophy as it is in the philosophy of Śāṅkara. It is undeniably true that Gauḍapāda is the grand preceptor of Śāṅkara and he follows this model philosopher to revolutionize basic Vedāntic Thought. By virtue of Śāṅkara's deep philosophical insights, the philosophical legacy of Gauḍapāda has been matured in the philosophy of Śāṅkara which he has inherited from his *parama guru* (grand teacher).

ⁱT.R.V. Murti asserts that "Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara revolutionized the Vedānta thought by establishing nondualism dialectically; they characterize phenomena as false appearance (*māyā*) and formulate the doctrine of three truths and two texts." *CPB*, p, 56 In a similar manner, T.M.P. Mahadevan has pointed out that both of them are advocates of Advaita thought. T.M.P. Mahadevan, *Gauḍapāda, A Study in Early Advaita*, University of Madras, Madras, 1954, p. 240

ⁱⁱ*Svapnajāgaritasthāne hyekamāhurmanīṣiṅaḥ / bhedānām hi samatvena prasiddhenaiva hetunā//Gauḍapāda Kārikā 2.5*

ⁱⁱⁱThe argument is as follows: Objects perceived in the waking state are not true. This is *pratijñā*. Because they are seen and this is *hetu*. As things seen in a

dream are not true, so the property seen belongs to things seen in the waking state- this is *hetupanaya*. Therefore, things seen in the waking state also are not true and this is *nigamana*. In this form of *pañcāvayavī nyāya* it is argued. A.G. Krishna Warriar, Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara: (A Study in Contrast), *Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute*, 1968, Vol. 48/49, Golden Jubilee Volume 1917-1967 (1968), pp. 179-186

^{iv}*Rjuvagrādibhāsamalātasponditam yathā/ gṛhaṅagrāhakābhāsam vijñānasponditam tathā// Gauḍapāda Kārikā, 4.47*

Aspandamānamalātamanābhāsamajam yathā/ aspandamānam vijñānamnābhāsamajam tathā// Gauḍapāda Kārikā, 4.48

Alāte spandamāne vai nābhāsā anyatobhavaḥ/

na tato 'nyatra nispanḍānnālatam praviśanti te
//Gauḍapāda Kārikā, 4.49

Na nirgatā alātātte dravyatvābhāvayogataḥ/
vijñāne 'pi tathaiḥ syurābhāsasyāviśeṣataḥ//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.50

Vijñāne spandamāne vai nābhāsā anyatobhuvah/
na tato 'nyatra nispanḍāna vijñānam viśanti te//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.51

Na nirgatāste vijñānādravyatvābhayogataḥ/
kāryakāraṇatābhāvādyato 'cintyāḥ sadaiva
te//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.52Gauḍapāda Kārikā(Ed.
with a complete translation into English, Notes,
Introduction and Appendices), Raghunath Damodar
Karmarkar, Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute,
Poona, 1953

^vGauḍapāda uses the term *dvayakāla* in the *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* 2.14. Here, the term 'dvaya' ('twofold') implies *grāhya* (perceptible)-*grāhaka* (percipient). Gauḍapāda maintains that the objects which exist as long as the thought (*citta*) exists are technically known as *cittakāla*. The objects which exist as long as the notion of the two (*grāhya* and *grāhaka*) remain are technically known as *dvayakāla*. Both *cittakāla* and *dvayakāla* objects are only imagined. In this regard, there lies no difference between them.

^{vi}*Cittakālā hi ye 'ntastu dvayakālāścāye vahih/
kalpitā evat e sarve viśeṣo
nānyahetukah//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.14*

*Avyāktā eva ye 'ntastusphuṭā eva ca ye vahih/
kalpitā evate sarve viśeṣastvindriyāntare//Gauḍapāda
Kārikā,2.15*

In the above *kārikā* the term *dvayakāla* literally means the 'duality-timers' but this term philosophically signifies, in the context of the said *kārikā*, the concept of the *grāhya-grāhaka*.

^{vii}*Vaitathyaṁ sarvabhāvām svapna āhurmanīṣiṇaḥ/
antaḥsthānāntu bhāvānām saṁvṛtatvena hetunā//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.5*

*Sarve dharma mṛṣā svapne kāyasyāntarṇidarśanāt/
saṁvṛte 'sminpradeśe vai bhūtānām darśanam kutaḥ//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.33*

^{viii}*Adīrghatvācca kālasya gatvā deśāna paśyati/
pratibuddhaśca vai sarvastasmindēse na
vidyate//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.2*

*Svapnadṛśyānām bhāvānāmanta
saṁvṛtasthānamityetadsiddham, yasmātprāptyeṣu
supta odakṣu svapnāpaśyanniva dṛśyata
ityetadāsakñyāha- na dehādvahirdēśāntara gatvā
svapnānpaśyati, yasmātsuptamātra eva
dehadeśādyojanaśatāntarite māsamātraprāpye deśe
svapnānpaśyanniva dṛśyate, na ca taddeśaprāpte
rāgamansya ca dīrgha kālo 'sti, ata adīrghatvācca
kālasya na svapnadrḡdeśāntara gachhati. Kinca,
pratibuddhaśca vai sarva svapnadṛk
svapnadarśanadeśe na vidyate. Yadi ca svapna
deśāntara gachhet, yasmindēse svapnānpaśyēt,
tatraiva pratibudhyeta. Na caitadasti. Rātrau supta
ahanīva bhāvānpaśyati, vahubhi sagato bhavati,
yaiśca sagata sa nairgrhyeta, na ca grhyata,
grhītaścettvāmadya tatopalabdhavanto vayamiti
brūyu, na caitadasti. Tasmāna deśāntara gachhati
svapne. Śāṅkara'sKārikābhāṣya onGauḍapāda
Kārikā,2.2*

^{ix}Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya remarks on the *Gauḍapāda Kārikā* 4.35 & 36 that "Gauḍapāda offers here some reasons in his support from the standpoint of the Vijñānavādīns showing that the external things are unreal; they are, however, false as the experience in dream, being cognizable only by mind (*cittadrśya*)". Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya, *Āgamaśāstra of Gauḍapāda* (Edited, Translated and Annotated), University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1943, pp. 23-24 (Introduction)

^x*Adāvante ca yannāsti vartamāne 'pi tattathā/
vitathaiḥsadrśāḥ santo 'vitathā
ivalakṣitāḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.6*

^{xi}Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya translates the term '*saprayojanatā*' as 'having some purpose' in his *Āgamaśāstra of Gauḍapāda* (Edited, Translated and Annotated), University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1943, p 20.

^{xii}*Sprayojanatā teṣām svapne vipratipadyate/
tasmādādyantavattvena mithyaiva khalu te smṛtāḥ//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.7*

Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya reads the verse as 'svapne 'pi pratipadyate for svapne vipratipadyate and translates it as "that the things have some purpose also in dream is known". Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya,

Āgamaśāstra of Gauḍapāda (Edited, Translated and Annotated), University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1943, pp. 19-20.

^{xiii} *Apūrva sthānidharmo hi yatha svarganivāsinām/
tānayaṁ prekṣate gatvā yathaiveha
suśikṣitaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.8*

(Śāṅkara's commentary to be attached)

^{xiv} *Yathā svapne dvayābhāsaṁ spandate māyayā
manaḥ/
tathā jāgraddvayābhāsaṁ spandate māyayā
manaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,3.29*

*Advayaṁ ca dvayābhāsaṁ manaḥ svapne na
saṁśayaḥ/*

*advayaṁ ca dvayābhāsaṁ tathā jāgaranna
saṁśayaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,3.30*

Śāṅkara has explained the concept of mind as identical with self in his commentary.

*Rajjurūpeṇa sarpa iva paramārthataātmarūpeṇa
advaya sat dvayābhāsa mana svapne, na saṁśaya. Na
hi svapne hastyādi grāhya tadgrāhak vā cakṣurādi,
dvaya vijñānavyatirekenāsti, jāgradapi
tathaiveyartha, paramārthasadvijñānamātrāviśeṣāt.
Śāṅkara's Kārikābhāṣya on Gauḍapāda Kārikā,3.30*

The content of these two verses is also repeated in the fourth chapter, verse no. 61 & 62.

The term *māyā* actually, here, requires a deep philosophical clarification to understand the philosophical significance of Gauḍapāda's thought. The concept of *māyā* in Gauḍapāda's philosophy is quite different from Śāṅkara's formulation of *māyā*. In the philosophy of Śāṅkara, the doctrine of *māyā* plays a key role. In the Śāṅkara's dialectic, the concept of *māyā* has a cosmological approach. The cosmological connotation of the concept of *māyā* does not imply the falsity or unreality of the world we live in. But in the philosophical formulation of Gauḍapāda, the situation is quite different. Because of Yogācāra influence, Gauḍapāda has ascribed a different sense to the concept of *māyā*. He has explained the multiplicity of this world in terms of illusion and mental vibrations (*citta spandana*). In the philosophy of Gauḍapāda, the term *māyā* has acquired an illusionistic approach. The ultimate culmination of the concept of *māyā*, in the

philosophy of Gauḍapāda, has taken place in the *Ajātivāda* of *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā*.

^{xv} *Āgamaśāstra of Gauḍapāda* (Edited, Translated and Annotated), University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1943, p. 146

^{xvi} *Utpādasyāprasiddhatvādajaṁ sarvamudāhṛtam/
Na ca bhūtādabhūtasya sambhavo'sti
kathamcana//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.38*

*Asajjāgarite drṣṭā svapne paśyati tanmayah/
asatsvapne'pi drṣṭā ca pratibuddho na
paśyati//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.39*

*Nāstyasadhetukamasatsadhetukaṁ tathā/
sacca sadhetukaṁ nāsti sadhetukamasatkutaḥ//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.40*

*...svapno jāgaritakāryamiti,
tatkathaumtpādāo'prasiddha iti ucyate śrṇu tatra
yathākāryakāraṇabhāvo'smābhirabhipreta iti. Asat
avidyamāna rajjusarpavadvikalpita vastu jāgarite
drṣṭvā tadbhāvabhāvitastanmaya svapne'pi
jāgaritavat grāhyagrāhakarūpeṇa vikalpayanpaśyati,
tathā asatsvapna'pi drṣṭvā ca pratibuddha na paśyati
avikalpayan, ca śabdāt. tathājāgarite'pi drṣṭvā
svapne na paśyati kadācidatyatha. Tasmājjāgarita
svapnaheturityucyate, na tu paramārthasaditi
kṛtvā. Śāṅkara's Kārikābhāṣya on Gauḍapāda
Kārikā,4.39*

^{xvii} *Ubhayaorapi vaitathyaṁ bhedānām sthānayoryadi/
ka etābudhyate bhedānko vai teṣāṁ vikalpakaḥ//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.11*

*Kalpayatyātmanātmānamātmā devaḥsvamāyayā/
sa eva budhyate bhedāniti
vedāntaniścayaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.12*

^{xviii} *Aniścītā yathā rajjurandhakāre vikalpitā/
sarpadhārādibhirbhāvaistadvadātmā
vikalpiṭaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.17*

*Niścītāyām yathā rajjvām viaklpo vinivartate/
rajjureveti cādvaitam
tadvadātmaviniścayaḥ//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,2.18*

^{xix} *Rjuvagrādibhāsamalātaspaditaṁ yathā/
grhaṇagrāhakābhāsaṁ vijñānaspanditaṁ tathā//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.47*

*Aspandamānamalātamānābhāsamajam yathā/
aspandamānam vijñānamānābhāsamajam tathā//
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.48*

*Alāte spandamāne vai nābhāsā anyatobhuvah/
na tato'nyatra nispandānnālatam praviśanti te*
//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.49

*Na nirgatā alātātte dravyatvābhāvayogataḥ/
vijñāne'pi tathaiva syurābhāsasyāvīśeṣataḥ//*
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.50

*Vijñāne spandamāne vai nābhāsā anyatobhuvah/
na tato'nyatra nispandāna vijñānam viśanti te//*
Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.51

*Na nirgatāste vijñānādravyatvābhayogataḥ/
kāryakāraṇatābhāvādyato 'cintyāḥ sadaiva*
te//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,4.52

^{xx}Nābhāvah, upalabdheḥ // Brahmasūtra 2.2.28

& Śāṅkara'sbhāṣya on this sūtra

^{xxi}Smṛtirūpaḥ paratra pūrvadrṣṭāvabhāṣah, Adhyasa
bhāṣya

^{xxii}Ekameva hi paramārthasatyam brahma:
vyavahāraviṣayamāpekṣikam satyam
mṛgatrṣṇikādyanṛtāpekṣayodakādi satyamuccate,
Taittiriya Upaniṣadbhāṣyam, 2.6

^{xxiii}A.G. Krishna Warriar, Gauḍapāda and Śāṅkara: (A
Study in Contrast), *Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental
Research Institute*, 1968, Vol. 48/49, Golden Jubilee
Volume 1917-1967 (1968), pp. 179- 186

^{xxiv}Svasidhhāntavyavasthāsthu dvaitino niścītā
drḍham/

parasparam viruddhyante tairayam na
viruddhyate//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,3.17

*Advaitam paramārtho hi dvaitam tadbheda ucyate/
teṣāmubhayathā dvaitam tenāyam na*
virudhyate//Gauḍapāda Kārikā,3.18

Vidhusekhar Bhattacharya makes a note on the above kārikā (verse) that "... so far as mere duality is concerned, hence there is no conflict between cause and effect is, in fact, no difference, the effect being merely a particular state of its cause. So, there is no independent existence of the effect apart from that of its cause. In the same way duality is a particular state or effect of non-duality, being an illusion. The only difference between us is that according to your duality is in both ways, in reality and also in appearance, while we say that though there is duality, no doubt, it is not in reality, it exists only in appearance."

Āgamaśāstra of Gauḍapāda(Edited, Translated and Annotated), University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1943, p. 60

^{xxv} Here, Gauḍapāda's basic philosophical hypothesis needs to be examined in order to understand clearly his philosophical position as why *ajātivāda* does not conflict with any other dualistic views. Richard King, "Śūnyatā and Ajāti": Absolutism and the Philosophies of Nāgārjuna and Gauḍapāda, *Journal of Indian Philosophy*, December, 1989, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 385-405

^{xxvi}There is nothing about which it can be said that it is produced. 7

^{xxvii}Janmādyasya yataḥ, *Brahmasūtra* 1.1.2

^{xxviii}Buddhist philosophers are of different opinions in this regard. They deny birth or *jāti* of anything in this empirical world. Nāgārjuna, in his *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, points out that *anirodhamanutpādam*. He intends to imply that there is neither origination nor destruction.

*Anirodham anutpādam anucchedam aśāsvatam, Anekārtham anānārtham anāgamam anirgamam, yaḥ pratīyasanutpādam prapañcopaśamamśivam desayāmāsa sambuddhaḥ tam vande vandatām varam*Dedicatory Verses, *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā of Nāgārjuna*(*The Philosophy of the Middle Way*), David J. Kalupahana, MLBD Publishers Private Limited, Delhi, 2015

In the above quoted first verse of the *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, Nāgārjuna, s philosophical standpoint of *Śūnyavāda* is luminously prominent. Vidhusekhara Sashtri has made a very crucial comment at this point that "...Gauḍapāda, too, has followed the same order in his well-known *kārikā*III.32: '*na nirodho na cotpattiḥ*'"Vidhusekhara Sashtri, *TheGauḍapāda-Kārikā on the MāṇḍūkyaUpaniṣad, Proceedings and Transactions of the Second Oriental Conference*, Calcutta, 1922, pp. 439-461

^{xxix}*Itaśca na jāyata kiñcit jajjāyamān vastu svata parata ubhayato vā sat asat sadasadvā na jāyata, na tasya kanacidapi prakāreṇa janma sabhavati. Na tāvatsvayamevāpariniṣpannātsvata*

svarūpātsvayameva jāyata, yathā ghaṭastasmādeva
ghaṭāt. Nāpi parata anyasmādanya, yathāghaṭātpata.
Tathā nobhayata, virodhāt,
yathāghaṭapaṭābhyāghaṭa paṭo vā na jāyate. Nanu
mṛdāghaṭo jāyate pītuśca putra, satyam, asti jāyata iti
pratyaya śabdaśca mūdhānām. Tāveva tu
śabdapratyayau vivekibhi parīkṣyeta- kim
satyamavatau, uta mṛṣā iti, yāvātā
parīkṣyamāṇeśabdapratyaviṣaya vastu
ghaṭaputrādīlakṣaṇa śabdāmātrameva tat,
'vācārambhaṇam' iti śrute. Śāṅkara's Kārikābhāṣya
on Gaudapāda Kārikā, 4.22

xxx Bhūtato 'bhūtato vā 'pi srjyamānesamāśrutiḥ/

Nīscitaṁ yuktīyuktaṁ ca yattadbhavati
netaram//Gaudapāda Kārikā, 3.23

Nanvajātivādina srṣṭipratipādikāśrutirna sagachha
te. vādham, vidyate srṣṭipratipādikāśruti, sā
tvanyaparā, 'upāya so 'vatāraya' ityavocāma.
Idānīmukte 'pi parihāre punaścoddaparihārau
vivakṣitārthe prati
srṣṭiśrutyakṣarāṇāmānulomyavirodhaśāṅkāmātrapar
ihārārthau. Bhūtata paramārthata srjyamāne vastuni,
abhūtata māyayā vāmāyā vineva srjyamāne vastuni
samā tulyāsrṣṭiśruti. Nanu gaṇamukhyayormukhye
śabdārthapratipattiryuktā, na,
anyathāsrṣṭeraprasiddhatvānniṣprajoyanavācca
ityavoācma. avidyāsrṣṭiṣayaiva sarvā gauṇī mukhyā
ca srṣṭi, na paramārthata, 'savāhyābhyantaro hyaja'
iti śruti. Tasmāt śrutyā nīscita yat
ekamevādvitīyamajamṛtamiti, yuktīyukta ca yuktyā ca
sapannam, tadevetyavocāma pūrvairgranthai, tadeva
śrutyartho bhavati, netarakta dācidapi kvacidapi.
Śāṅkara's Kārikābhāṣya on Gaudapāda Kārikā, 3.23

xxxī 'Savāhyābhyantaro hyaja'

xxxīi Swami Nikhilananda, *The Māṇḍūkyaopaniṣad with
Gaudapāda's Kārikā and Śāṅkara's Commentary*
(Translated and Annotated), Sri Ramakrishna
Ashrama, Mysore, 1949, p.185

xxxīiii Samvṛtyā jāyate sarvamāśvataṁnāsti tena vai/

Sadbhāvena hyajam sarvamuchhedastena nāsti
vai//Gaudapāda Kārikā, 4.57

xxxīiv Gaudapāda in his *Gaudapāda Kārikā*, has
wonderfully explained his philosophical view

regarding this matter. Let me quote few lines from his
kārikā:

Āśramāstrividhā hīnamadhyamotkṛṣṭadrṣṭayah/
upāsanopadiṣṭeyam
tadarthamanukampayā//Gaudapāda Kārikā, 3.16

xxxv G.R. Malkani, *Metaphysics of Advaita Vedanta*,
The Indian Institute of Philosophy, Amalner,
Madras, 1961, p. 213.

xxxvi T.M.P. Mahadevan, *Gaudapāda, A Study in Early
Advaita*, University of Madras, Madras, 1954, pp.
231-232.